

A Critique on Shashi Deshpande's The Dark Holds No Terrors

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Abstract

This paper deals with the critical analysis of Shashi Deshpande’s The Dark Holds No Terrors. This novel delineates about women subjugation in patriarchal society Sarita (Saru), the combatant of the novel faces the problem of gender discrimination, which affects the Indian women in general. Saru doesn’t get any kind of solace in her childhood. She yearns for freedom but after her marriage, she is physically and mentally tormented by her husband Manohar. She cannot tolerate the beast like behavior of her husband. So, she reconstitutes to her parental home. Due to her elopement, Saru lost the love of her father and mother. Mother died without exonerating her. She feels emptiness in her mind. This novel, manifestly, structures the quest for life and self identity of Sarita.

Keywords: Subjugation, Self-identity, Patriarchal domination, Gender discrimination.

Shashi Deshpande, a famous Indian feminist writer, who has contributed much to gender studies. She was born in 1938 in Dharwad, Karnataka. She is the second daughter of the famous Kannada dramatist and writer Sriranga. Educated in Bombay and Bangalore, Deshpande has degrees in Economics and Law. In Mumbai, she studied journalism at Vidya Bhavan and worked for a couple of months as a journalist for the magazine On Lookers.

She published her first collection of short stories in 1978. Some of her famous novels are *If I Die Today* (1982), *Come up and Be Dead* (1989), *Roots and Shadows* (1983), *Matter of Time* (1996), *Small Remedies* (2000), *The Binding Vine* (1992), *Moving On* (2004), *In the Country of Deceit* (2008). She won the Shakitya Akademi Award for the novel *That Long Silence* in 1990 and the Padmashri Award in 2009. Her novel *Shadow Play* was short listed for The Hindu Literary Prize in 2014. Deshpande has written four children books, number of short stories and nine novels besides several perceptive essays. Her first novel *The Dark Holds No Terrors* was published in 1980.

Sarita (Saru) is the protagonist of the novel. She is well educated and reputed doctor. She is a sincere social worker praised by everyone in the surroundings. Her childhood is not much happier than other children around her age. Even in her marriage life, she is not happy as expected by her. The novel opens with Saru’s return to her parental home after fifteen years. Saru is an unwelcomed guest in her own home. She feels alienated, because her father loves Madhav,

who is not even his own blood. She has become emotionless women. She did not feel sorry for her mother's death. Though she cares for her children, she abandoned them because of husband's tortures. One day she meets her childhood friends Smita and Nalu. Smita a married woman totally dependent on her husband economically. Nalu is a spinster and a working woman. Saru compares herself with her friends and finds that she is better than the two. Finally she is bound to realize herself and returns to Manohar and her children.

Characterization is an important factor to develop a full length plot. Shashi Deshpande has used both round and flat characters in this novel. Saru, the heroine of the novel is a round character. The incidents in this novel almost revolve around the life of Saru. Through Saru, we come to know the minor characters of this novel. At first she has no confidence and grip in her life. As the plot develops she gradually moulds her and becomes a full-fledged woman in the final part of the novel. Manohar, the husband of Saru, is a flat character in this novel. Though, Manohar and Saru have had love marriage, their marital life is not a successful one because, Manohar plays a dual role at home. He behaves like a beast at night and a normal being in the morning. "You cook and he cleans, it's a partnership, wordless, uncomplaining and perfect. A tacit understanding. As all good partnerships should be. How does it feel when your wife earns not only the butter but the bread as well?" (35-36).

Manohar behaves like a sadist. He feels humiliated when people give more respects to Saru. He thinks that he is belittled by others. He feels inferior when he thinks that he cannot compete Saru economically. Saru's mother is portrayed as a dominating woman. She used to suppress her husband to such an extent that, Saru's father is reduced merely to a log of wood at home. He does not show any kind of reaction to the insults of his wife. And so, when Saru returns home, her father does not ask her anything, he does not even care to ask about his grandchildren. At first Saru cannot understand about the incidents happening in her life. But when she is left idle and alone in her home, she becomes gradually aware of the fact that the faults lie within her. And she feels that she shall not behave like her mother. She should not violate the masculinity of Manohar which leads him to behave like a sadist.

Saru, often thinks about her brother Dhruva in this novel, who died long ago during his childhood days. Dhruva is a younger brother to Saru. Dhruva, as a child was very much scared of darkness. He used to sleep near Saru because of his nightmares. After the death of Dhruva, Saru often has the nightmares about Dhruva. But she cannot discuss it with anyone. She is guilty, about her brother's death. Although, she knows that she did not kill him.

You killed your brother.

I didn't. Truly I Didn't. It was an accident. I loved him, my little brother. I tried to save him. Truly I tried. But I couldn't. And I ran away. Yes, I ran way, I admit that. But I didn't kill him.

How do you know you didn't kill him? How do you know? (146)

Even though, she abandons her children Renu and Abhi for a short time. She is always thinking about them in her home whether they eat properly or not. The only communication between them is letters.

Smita and Nalu are the friends of Saru. Shashi Deshpande has created Smita as very feeble character who is submissive to her husband and she borrows money from Saru without the knowledge of her husband. This shows the pathetic condition of Smita. Nalu, who is a spinster economically independent, has not experienced one aspect of life and has no respect in the society. Some other minor characters are Boozie, Prof. Kulkarni who play a very little role but Deshpande has used these characters to enhance the plot.

Shashi Deshpande gives more importance to mother-daughter relationship in this novel. It is based on gender partiality. Saru, the daughter of the family is deprived of parental care and

fondness. Her mother is deeply attached to her younger brother Dhruva. Saru has been accused for the death of her brother Dhruva. Saru's mother never rendered any kindness towards her rather she complains that Saru killed her brother. "You killed him, why didn't you die? Why are you alive, when he's dead?" (191). This incident creates a permanent rift between Saru and her mother. This makes Saru go against her mother in her matrimonial relationship.

Gender discrimination is an important factor which the protagonist endures throughout the novel. According to Indian family conventions and traditions parents always prefer a boy child to a girl child. Saru's family is an orthodox Brahmin family. From childhood, Saru undergoes several kinds of restrictions. When Saru starts protesting, her mother retaliated that,

Don't go out in the sun, you'll get even darker.

Whocares?

We have to care if you don't. We have to get you married.

I don't want to get married.

Will you live with us all your life?

Why not?

You can't

And Dhruva?

He's different. He's a boy. (45)

This novel shows the typical minds of Indian families and depicts the gender discrimination.

The Dark Hold No Terrors not only represents the patriarchal domination in the society but also the women-over women domination. Indian girls in the society generally do not have any rights and equality in choosing their education and life partner. Saru wishes to study medicine but her mother is against her wish. When Saru wants to marry Manohar who belongs to low caste her mother rebuked her for being in her own way, not being submissive to her parents. Her mother is illustrated as the representation of male chauvinism.

Deshpande's feministic perspectives can be seen through the discussion on Shakespeare, the greatest dramatists for all times. She illustrates that Shakespeare plays are men oriented. Shakespeare has painted all the men characters stronger but women characters are dependent to men. "It is the way he made the woman's personality merge into the stronger colours of a man's personality. Look at Hamlet, Lear, Othello. And look at Ophelia, Cordelia, Desdemona. Poor, feeble shadows" (156).

Self-realization is a most significant aspect in this novel which modifies the life of Saru. The author painted the theme of self-identity in the final part of the novel. She is fabricated into the enigma of human existence. She has been battling with her thoughts of salvation. She has to kill the horror of thoughts that haunted her often. She later realizes that she is responsible for the savage behavior of Manohar towards her. She is economically better than Manohar which makes him feel inferior. She relates her life with mathematic equation, later she apprehends that there is no possible way to get equality in the Indian society.

$a+b$ they told us in mathematics is equal to $b+a$. But here $a+b$ was not, definitely not equal to $b+a$. It became a monstrously unbalanced equation, lopsided, unequal, impossible. But is that the only reason, or would it have happened in any case, what happened to us later, he being what he is and I being what I am? I have a feeling I will never know the answer to that one. (42)

Saru's parental home helps her to find her own identity. So she returns to Bombay and restores herself the pride of being a physician. She accomplishes the assertion of strong will and confidence in her own self. Thus she grasps to trust herself. "My life is my own...somehow she felt as if she had found it now, the connecting link" (220).

Narrative technique carries a special place in this novel. It helps the readers to understand the plot well. Shashi Deshpande has used the first person narration in this novel. It is through the eyes of Saru, the readers can see other sub-characters in this novel. This story shifts from past to present and from present to past. This plot has been interwoven with retrospective techniques. This novel is divided into four parts. The novelist has used simple language in her work. In the end Saru accepts the life as it is, she does not attempt to change the character of Manohar but the changes take place within her. These aspects fascinate the readers towards the novel.

Shashi Deshpande is a feminist as well as an anti-feminist in the same novel. Saru is a rebellious child and wife. In the beginning, the views of feminism can be seen through the words of distressed Saru. When Saru's mother speaks about her grandmother she says, that the grandmother has been forsaken by her husband and so she is left alone with her daughters. Her father takes them home and helps them. During those times, women used to accept the life as it is without complaining about life. They tell that they suffer because of their fate. "If only I could say that. My luck. My fate. Written on my forehead. Will that help me to accept, to passively endure?" (70). Saru feels irritated and question that why women should endure everything without complaining about life. This shows the feministic approach of the novelist.

But later in this novel, Saru understands that women should not violate the masculinity of men.

And, I assure you, it isn't worth it. He'll suffer, you'll suffer and so will the children. Women's magazines will tell you that a marriage should be equal partnership. That's nonsense. Rubbish. No partnership can ever be equal. It will always be unequal, but take care that it's unequal in favour of your husband. If the scales tilt in your favour, god help you, both of you. (137)

From this passage the anti-feministic views of Shashi Deshpande can be seen.

Saru leaves Manohar for a while. Her short time stay in father's home helps her analyse herself and it leads to self-realization. This novel gives the full picture of Sarita. The character of Sarita represents the whole womenfolk of the society who generally undergo such evils – gender discrimination, patriarchal domination and physical violation. Her quest for identity shows the real position of women in the Indian society. Thus, Shashi Deshpande's *The Dark Holds No Terrors* is a typical Indian novel.

Work Cited

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